

INTER-NATIONAL HARMONY - THE BASIS OF SOCIAL STABILITY.

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Abstract: This article analyzes inter-ethnic harmony and its role in ensuring social stability. The author discusses the coexistence of representatives of different nationalities in a society in the spirit of mutual respect and harmony, the impact of this process on political, economic and cultural stability. The importance of state policy, education and culture in strengthening national unity is also highlighted. The article analyzes the role of harmony in social development, its role in preventing conflicts and the main factors on the way to building a strong society.

Keywords: Inter-ethnic harmony, social stability, national unity, harmony, cultural diversity, tolerance, peace, social stability, state policy, mutual respect, integration, cooperation, development, conflict prevention.

MILLATLARARO TOTUVLIK- IJTIMOIIY BARQARORLIK ASOSI.

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Annotatsiya: Mazkur maqolada millatlararo totuvlik va uning ijtimoiy barqarorlikni ta'minlashdagi o'rni tahlil etiladi. Muallif jamiyatda turli millat vakillarining o'zaro hurmat va hamjihatlik ruhida yashashi, bu jarayonning siyosiy, iqtisodiy va madaniy barqarorlikka ta'siri haqida fikr yuritadi. Shuningdek, milliy birdamlikni mustahkamlashda davlat siyosati, ta'lim va madaniyatning ahamiyati yoritiladi. Maqolada totuvlikning ijtimoiy taraqqiyotga xizmat qilishi, nizolarning oldini olishdagi roli va mustahkam jamiyat barpo etish yo'lidagi asosiy omillar tahlil qilinadi.

Kalit so'zlar: Millatlararo totuvlik, ijtimoiy barqarorlik, milliy birdamlik, hamjihatlik, madaniy xilma-xillik, bag'rikenglik, tinchlik, jamiyat barqarorligi, davlat siyosati, o'zaro hurmat, integratsiya, hamkorlik, taraqqiyot, mojarolarning oldini olish.

**МЕЖНАЦИОНАЛЬНАЯ ГАРМОНИЯ – ОСНОВА СОЦИАЛЬНОЙ
СТАБИЛЬНОСТИ.**

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Аннотация: В статье анализируется межнациональное согласие и его роль в обеспечении социальной стабильности. Автор размышляет о сосуществовании представителей разных национальностей в обществе в духе взаимного уважения и согласия, а также о влиянии этого процесса на политическую, экономическую и культурную стабильность. В нем также подчеркивается важность государственной политики, образования и культуры в укреплении национального единства. В статье анализируется вклад гармонии в общественный прогресс, ее роль в предотвращении конфликтов, а также ключевые факторы построения сильного общества.

Ключевые слова: Межэтническое согласие, социальная стабильность, национальное единство, сплоченность, культурное многообразие, толерантность, мир, социальная стабильность, государственная политика, взаимное уважение, интеграция, сотрудничество, развитие, предотвращение конфликтов.

Social stability is an important factor in the evolutionary development of society. Therefore, when it comes to interethnic relations and development, the issue of social stability is first of all brought to mind. However, this stability should not be equated with conservatism or stagnation, orthodox approaches are not suitable for it. Although social stability is sometimes formed by combining different events and approaches, it does not accept permanent connections in society as absolute. On the contrary, the existence of internal contradictions in this process is considered a natural state. Therefore, stability should be ensured not through external pressure, dictatorship or

violence, but on the basis of the primacy of democratic principles and legal values in relations between the individual, society and the state. In particular, civil society and modern ethno-political paradigms require the formation of social stability on the basis of legal and democratic values. In recent years, one of the priority areas of state policy has been to ensure interethnic harmony and tolerance in society, to strengthen the atmosphere of friendship and the feeling of a large multinational single family, to educate young people in the spirit of love and devotion to the Motherland, respect for national and universal values, and to expand cultural and educational ties with foreign countries. The provisions of the Constitution of the Republic of Uzbekistan are being actively implemented in life, which declare and guarantee that citizens of the Republic of Uzbekistan constitute the people of Uzbekistan, regardless of their nationality, as well as that the Republic of Uzbekistan will respect the language, customs and traditions of the nations and peoples living on its territory, and will create conditions for their development. For these purposes, the Committee on Interethnic Relations and Friendship with Foreign Countries was established under the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan, which carries out its activities and consistently implements the state policy on ensuring interethnic harmony and tolerance in society. Today, more than 130 nationalities and ethnic groups living in our country adhere to 16 religious confessions. Classes are held in seven languages in state educational institutions of our country. The programs of the National Television and Radio Company of Uzbekistan are broadcast in a total of twelve languages, and newspapers and magazines are published in more than ten languages. 156 national cultural centers operate under the Committee on Interethnic Relations and Friendship with Foreign Countries under the Ministry of Culture. In addition, there are about 2,300 religious organizations belonging to 16 religious confessions in our country. Using the equal rights and opportunities provided by the Constitution and laws of the Republic of Uzbekistan, they work effectively in various sectors of the economy and the social sphere, in the fields of science and culture, making a worthy contribution to the prosperity of our Motherland and strengthening its independence, as well as to enhancing the prestige and image of the republic in the international arena. The adoption of the Concept of State Policy of the Republic of Uzbekistan in the field of interethnic relations today serves as an important factor in ensuring social stability. An analysis of the pace of implementation of priority areas, large-scale democratic reforms, political, economic, social, spiritual liberalization and significant successes achieved in other aspects of public life gives all the grounds to emphasize that the people of Uzbekistan are united around a single idea - a single goal of achieving noble goals and extremely important tasks in the priority areas of development of the Republic of Uzbekistan.

At the same time, in the context of ongoing globalization and transformation in international and regional relations, the intensification of economic, political, national, religious and other conflicts in the world, and the increasing confrontation in information and cyberspace, a number of urgent issues remain that require their resolution in the field of further development of interethnic relations and friendly relations with foreign countries, including:

Further increase in the level of interaction between state bodies and organizations, local executive authorities with civil society institutions in the field of further development of interethnic relations and friendly relations with foreign countries;

Monitoring the state of interethnic relations in the field of early prevention and prevention of possible conflict situations and disagreements in society as a basis for organizing activities to prevent them.

Improving the work on training, retraining and advanced training of specialists of state bodies, as well as employees of other organizations, in the field of further development of interethnic relations and friendly relations with foreign countries. Interethnic harmony means peaceful and harmonious coexistence of representatives of different nationalities and ethnic groups. This process is achieved through mutual understanding, cooperation and respect for cultural diversity in society. Harmony not only ensures social cohesion, but also has a positive impact on the economic development, political stability and cultural development of the country. Social stability is a state aimed at maintaining the internal balance of society, preventing conflicts and protecting the interests of all citizens. Interethnic harmony is one of the main foundations of this stability. If injustice, discrimination or conflict arises between representatives of different nationalities in society, this can lead to social instability. Therefore, strengthening interethnic relations is an important condition for ensuring stability.

1. Public policy – Any state should develop effective legal mechanisms to maintain interethnic harmony. The equal rights of citizens, regardless of their nationality, are a fundamental condition for the principles of social justice.

2. Education system – It is important to educate the younger generation in the spirit of tolerance, intercultural dialogue and cooperation. Programs promoting interethnic harmony should be implemented in schools and higher education institutions.

3. Cultural exchange – Respect and understanding of each other's values are strengthened through cultural events, festivals and art conferences between representatives of different nationalities.

4. Mass media – The press, television and internet platforms should create content that promotes interethnic harmony. Materials that incite conflicts or promote hatred should not be allowed.

There are certain differences between social stability and democratic values. The first has a tendency towards generalization, even unification, while the second may require absolute freedom. The rational combination of these two approaches is the task of the new ethnopolitical paradigm. Issues of social stability have not yet been the subject of scientific, socio-philosophical research. In fact, the ethnopolitical paradigm and achievements in interethnic relations are reflected in social stability. In order to ensure social stability, it is important to analyze the factors that directly affect it and the indirect factors that serve to eliminate instability. Indirect factors include the formation of ethnopolitical paradigms, the establishment of institutions aimed at the development of national and cultural development, the strengthening of international integration ties, the development of international values, and the provision of equality between nations. These measures serve to stabilize interethnic relations. If polyethnic states ignore these factors, it will be difficult to achieve social stability. At the same time, some of the factors that directly affect may also be dangerous and destructive. For example, approaches such as making territorial claims without taking into account the existing reality, interpreting a certain historical figure as a representative of only one nation, contrasting the cultural values of different peoples, presenting one's own culture and language as the most ancient, seeking the causes of decline only in representatives of other nations, or considering oneself to be always humiliated can cause interethnic conflicts. There are an extremely large number of indirect factors, which can be related to economic, political, cultural-domestic, professional, religious, moral values, lifestyle, ideological views and mentality. In fact, interethnic conflicts and social instability in the world are mainly caused by such indirect factors. Therefore, any society should pay special attention to maintaining and strengthening interethnic harmony. Today, there is almost no state that has not written the principle of equal rights into its constitution or does not seek to protect it. However, the famous sociologist P. Sorokin noted that “there are no national problems and interethnic inequality, but there is a general problem of inequality caused by various manifestations of general social factors.” According to the scientist, there is no purely national problem, it is always the result of general social, that is, religious, economic, intellectual, legal, household, professional, territorial and other factors. Anyone who wants to fight national inequality must first of all fight against social inequality. In fact, this is one of the basic principles of social stability. If someone wants to ensure interethnic stability, he must, first of all, try to strengthen social stability. This

fundamental principle does not deny the existence of certain disagreements, conflicts and contradictions. Just as any social process is unique, social instability also has its own characteristics. Therefore, preventing and eliminating instability is one of the important conditions for sustainable development.

Socio-political stability creates a solid foundation for the effective implementation of political reforms in the state and society. This creates the necessary conditions for ensuring the effective functioning of the institutions of the political system, controlling the implementation of laws, strengthening public order, ensuring peace and security. In turn, ensuring stability in society and the consistency of state policy are one of the important factors that distinguish Uzbekistan as an independent state. It also expands the possibilities for large-scale reforms, economic growth and attracting investment. In order to ensure political stability in a multinational society, it is important to strengthen cooperation between nations and religions, to find ways to achieve political agreement. In this regard, preventing interethnic conflicts, predicting them and taking necessary measures are crucial for maintaining the integrity of the state. For example, the social instability and interethnic conflicts that arose as a result of the collapse of the USSR serve as one of the illustrative examples of the consequences of this process. Therefore, every society must constantly strive to ensure interethnic harmony and stability. Interethnic relations are an integral part of social relations, and together with them they undergo processes of change, development and renewal. Therefore, any national relations ultimately enter the sphere of social relations and create the need to solve various problems in society. Although national relations have their own functional characteristics, the mechanisms for regulating and resolving them, as well as their main essence, are closely related to social relations. The inextricable link between specific processes and general trends means that, in particular, the regulation and resolution of interethnic relations through broad social relations should be considered as a factor in strengthening social stability in society. Therefore, ensuring interethnic harmony and social solidarity is one of the important conditions for the development of any stable society. In our opinion, to ensure social stability, the state needs the following characteristics: a) a sense of belonging to the nation; b) consistency of the form of government; c) a gradual and orderly change of the ruling elite; d) the presence of checking and opposing forces to maintain the balance of government structures; d) the practice of multi-party democracy with a framework that allows the opposition to function effectively; e) the presence of a large middle class. There are various approaches and ideas about regulating relations between nations and peoples and social classes. One of the main reasons for this can be explained by the fact that in world political history, peoples that had their own place fell into the clutches of colonialism,

and by the 20th century, as a result of the further strengthening of the awareness of national identity and the desire for independence, new independent states emerged on the world map.

In conclusion, it is worth noting that interethnic harmony is an important factor in the stability and consistent development of any society. It is a key factor in ensuring social stability and serves to strengthen mutual respect, cooperation and solidarity between different nations and peoples. Social stability, in turn, plays an important role in ensuring the economic, political and cultural development of the state. Therefore, measures aimed at maintaining and developing interethnic harmony are necessary not only to prevent disagreements within society, but also for the development of the country as a whole. Ensuring interethnic harmony requires strengthening the principles of equality, respect for cultural diversity and social justice. Interethnic harmony and social stability are closely related concepts, which are the basis of peace, prosperity and development in society. Therefore, every state and society should pay special attention to supporting and developing these principles.

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